

Investigating Students' Historical Literacy Through the Lens of Gender: An Overview

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Abstract

Background: Historical literacy is an essential competency in empowering young people to understand the past critically, reflect on the present, and make responsible decisions for the future. While existing studies primarily emphasise institutional or curricular comparisons, limited attention has been given to gender, despite its potential influence on how students interpret and reconstruct historical events.

Objective of the Study: This study aims to provide an overview of the level of historical literacy among 11th-grade senior high school students in West Java, Indonesia.

Methodology: The study involved 551 students, including 209 male and 342 female respondents, who completed an online historical literacy test via Google Form. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics to determine literacy levels and inferential statistics, including the Mann-Whitney test, to examine gender-based differences. Data normality was assessed with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

Results: Females achieved a higher mean historical literacy score ($M=61.1$, $SD=12.47$) compared to males ($M=59.95$, $SD=14.69$). A total of 60.4% of both males and females fall into the low category. The Mann-Whitney U value is 34,251.000, with an Asymptotic Significance value of 0.396, which is greater than 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the two groups.

Conclusion: The statistical tests show that the low level of historical literacy indicates challenges related to the dominance of rote memorisation in teaching, curriculum design, and the social context. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in historical literacy levels between male and female students.

Unique Contribution: This study provides findings on students' historical literacy levels by gender and addresses a research gap in both local and global contexts.

Key Recommendation: Further research is recommended to explore the influence of pedagogical preparation and professional development on historical literacy, the role of digital resources and online platforms in shaping students' historical understanding, and the variation of outcomes across different educational and cultural contexts.

Keywords – Historical literacy, senior high school students, gender, history teaching, literacy.

Introduction

Literacy, once limited to reading and writing, has expanded across various fields of knowledge, leading to terms such as financial, mathematical, technological, and historical literacy. The concept of historical literacy confirms history teaching as a process to develop historical awareness and as a key concept in preserving cultural heritage (Yulianto et al., 2024) .

In the Indonesian context, historical literacy is positioned as a central objective of history education, especially for high school students. Senior high school students are expected to acquire the ability to critically evaluate and effectively present historical information through oral, written, digital, and non-digital media. Maposa & Wassermann (2009) affirm that literacy in history education refers to the ability to read and write while studying history. Nokes (2012) stated that historical literacy is the capacity to negotiate or read and create or write the kinds of text that are valued in the past, to gather and weigh evidence from sources, to make decisions, using historical accounts to solve problems, and to make interpretations of the past. Historical literacy denotes the capacity to read, source, corroborate, contextualise, and use historical concepts rather than generic reading skills.

Studies in Indonesia reveal low historical literacy levels among senior high school and first-year university students. In Sukoharjo, only 1% (eight students) achieved an excellent rating, while the majority were rated poor, very poor, and failed (Purwanta, 2023) . In Ambarawa, 54% of senior high school students demonstrated low historical literacy (Yulianto et al., 2024). At the university level, the study shows that the literacy level of first-year university students is low (Kumalasari et al., 2022).

The study on the difference of literacy scores based on gender conducted by Tiarina et al. (2022) showed that the mean literacy score for female students was 62.50%, which was higher than that of male students, at 26.27%. Similarly, Syamsuri & Bancong (2022) found out that female students scored significantly higher than male students. This study concludes that female students have a positive perspective on reading, with high intrinsic motivation and task-focused behaviour, which better affects their literacy.

Previous studies on historical literacy have focused on comparing it across institutions, but differences by gender have not been clearly identified. Moreover, studies examining differences in historical literacy levels between males and females in either local or global contexts have not been conducted. Thus, the present study aims to explore the level of historical literacy and analyse the differences in historical literacy between male and female students.

Research Methods

This study employed a quantitative research design with descriptive and inferential statistical tests. The respondents took an online literacy test administered through Google Form at the same time. Google Form offers numerous advantages for conducting surveys; it can be distributed easily via links, allowing for quick data collection from a broad audience (Siva et al., 2019). In addition, Google Forms is a free tool, making it an economical choice, especially for this research, which has a large sample size. Descriptive statistical test measured the overall level of historical literacy, while the inferential statistical test measured the differences in historical literacy between male and female students.

Data Collecting and Instrument

The 551 Year 11 senior high school students in West Java, Indonesia, took a historical literacy test for this study. The researcher randomly sampled 209 male respondents and 342 female respondents. The collected data were then analysed using descriptive statistics to determine the mean, standard deviation, and overall score distribution. The 10 essay questions, designed based on the Learning Outcomes of Phase F in the National Curriculum, assessed students' historical literacy skills. The instrument was aligned with the historical literacy indicators from Maposa & Wassermann (2009) shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Blueprint of Historical Literacy Instrument

Literacy Dimension	Code	Indicator	Number
Knowledge	K	Knowing the background, location, chronology, and impact of historical events in historical texts	1, 3, and 4
Conceptual Understanding	CU	Understanding the flow of periodisation, concepts of change and continuity, as well as moral judgments in an event	2, 5, and 6
Source Work	SW	Analysing primary sources in the text, contextualise events in the text with current conditions, and evaluate the article	7, 8, 9, and 10

Data Analysis Technique

This study used descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyze the data. In the descriptive analysis, the data were explained using the mean, which was categorised into five categories, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Score Range

No.	Category	Interval
1	Very High	86-100
2	High	76-86
3	Moderate	60-75
4	Low	55-59
5	Very Low	≤ 54

In an inferential statistical test, the researchers first carried out a normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test because the study involved more than 100 students (Cresswell, 2016). The result of the prerequisite test showed that a p-value < 0.001 means that the data were not normally distributed. Following the tests, the researchers used the Mann-Whitney test to assess differences in scores between male and female students. It is appropriate to compare two independent groups with data in such a condition (Nakazono et al., 2024).

Results

Senior High School Students' Level of Historical Literacy

Based on the descriptive statistical test, the level of historical literacy among senior high school students has a mean score of 60.69, with the most frequently occurring score being 50. The standard deviation is 13.37, indicating considerable variation in literacy levels among the respondents. Therefore, the respondents' level of historical understanding is uneven. The minimum score is 0.00, while the maximum score is 90. A variance of 178.433 indicates that the respondents' historical literacy levels vary widely and are not concentrated around a single point.

Regarding the historical literacy levels across the entire sample, 34.1% are in the high category, 30.1% in the moderate category, 30.3% in the low category, 4.2% in the very low category, and 1.3% in the very high category. The frequency distribution of respondents across these categories can be seen in the table below (Table 3).

Table 3

Distribution of Historical Literacy Level Categories

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Very Low	23	4.2	4.2
Low	333	60.4	60.4
Moderate	111	20.1	20.1
High	77	14.0	14.0
Very High	7	1.3	1.3
Total	551	100.0	100.0

Based on Table 3, there are 84.8% in the moderate to very low category. To identify the distribution of respondents' scores within the range of 0–100 can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4

Distribution of Historical Literacy Level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid 0.00	3	0.5	0.5

10.00	4	0.7	0.7
20.00	4	0.7	0.7
30.00	3	0.5	0.5
40.00	9	1.6	1.6
50.00	167	30.3	30.3
60.00	166	30.1	30.1
70.00	111	20.1	20.1
80.00	77	14.0	14.0
90.00	7	1.3	1.3
Total	551	100.0	100.0

Based on Table 4, scores of 50.00 and 60.00 dominate the distribution with frequencies of 167 (30.3%) and 166 (30.1%), respectively; nearly 60% of the data fall into these two categories. A score of 70.00 is also quite significant, with 111 entries (20.1%). Low scores ranging from 0.00 to 40.00 have very small frequencies, each less than 2%. The cumulative percentage shows that 84.8% of the data are at or below 70.00. The maximum score of 90.00 has only seven entries (1.3%). This data distribution indicates that most scores are concentrated in the mid-range (50.00 to 70.00), with few at the extreme ends. To see the number of respondents who answered each question correctly, please refer to Table 6 below.

Table 5

Proportion of Correct Responses by Question

Number	Dimension	Percentage
1	K	7.97
2	CU	10.73
3	K	57.56
4	K	71.06
5	CU	76.09
6	CU	71.06
7	SW	64.23
8	SW	55.28
9	SW	65.20
10	SW	76.91

Based on Table 6, questions 7 to 10 refer to the SW dimension, with the highest percentage of respondents answering correctly at 65.41%. The dimension of CU is represented by questions 2, 5, and 6, showing that 52.63% of respondents answered correctly. Meanwhile, the dimension of K is represented through the question numbers 1, 3, and 4, showing that the respondents answered correctly at a rate of 45.53%. This indicates that SW is the highest-performing dimension compared to the other two.

The difference in historical literacy levels based on gender

The descriptive test results show a difference in mean scores between males and females. Females have a higher mean historical literacy score compared to males. Females scored a mean of 61.1

with a standard deviation of 12.47, while males scored a mean of 59.95 with a standard deviation of 14.69.

To find out the percentage of the score based on the categories, a crosstab test was conducted. The result demonstrates that the percentage of total scores for both males and females in the low category is 60.4%, in the moderate category 20.1%, high category 14%, very low category 4.2%, and very high category 1.3%. Detailed data can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 1.

Historical Literacy Score Categories by Gender

The result confirms that 22.7% of male students and 37.7% of female students have low literacy. In the high score category, the percentage of females is slightly higher than that of males, at 8.5% compared to 5.4%. To examine differences in historical literacy by gender, the researchers used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normality because the sample size exceeded 100. The result shows a significance value (p-value) < 0.001. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the data are not normally distributed.

To further examine differences in historical literacy by gender, the researchers used the Mann-Whitney U test to compare two independent groups. Based on the analysis result, the Mann-Whitney U value is 34,251 with an Asymptotic Significance (2-tailed) value of 0.396. The significance value is greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that there is no significant difference between male and female respondents' scores.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that most senior high school students (60.4%) across genders demonstrate a low level of historical literacy. This outcome suggests that inadequate historical literacy is not incidental but rather symptomatic of broader instructional practices. The persistence of rote memorisation as the predominant pedagogical approach, coupled with the limited integration of sourcing and contextualization, constrains students' capacity to develop analytical and evaluative capacities. Moreover, the low level of historical literacy is likely to affect their

historical awareness (Roberts, 2013) . It fosters a population that is disconnected from its past and unable to form a strong sense of identity. The high percentage of students with low literacy levels underscores an urgent need to reorient history education toward more inquiry-based and critical approaches.

The dimension with the lowest score percentage (45.53%) is the historical knowledge dimension. Historical knowledge fosters students' critical engagement with the past through narratives, context, and methodologies. It encompasses two sub-dimensions: knowledge of events, which involves analysing the contested and shifting nature of historical facts, and knowledge of narratives, which concerns understanding how historical accounts are constructed and interpreted. The development of historical narratives refers to how students develop their historical narratives through diverse perspectives and interpretations (Lee, 2005). Knowledge related to the cognitive sphere, which enables individuals to understand and interpret historical events, texts and their broader context (Maposa & Wassermann, 2009). Akhmetova et al. (2024) stated that the development of knowledge is inseparable from basic cognitive abilities, including attention, perception, memory, and thinking. Attention serves as the gateway to learning, while perception enables individuals to interpret sensory input meaningfully. Memory functions as both a temporary holding system through working memory and a long-term repository for consolidation and retrieval. These cognitive processes are interdependent and must be activated for effective learning. However, as Purwanta (2023) emphasise, the dominance of rote memorisation in history lessons often undermines students' comprehension, limiting their ability to engage in deeper historical understanding. In West Java, some teachers assumed that history was about memorisation, which led to low student engagement. To overcome this, teachers can vary their teaching methods based on student involvement, especially in helping students remember and interpret the new information in their own language.

The next dimension, showing low scores, is Conceptual Understanding (CU) with a mean percentage of 52.63%. This indicates that more than half of the respondents still lack this competence. A solid conceptual understanding is essential for improving historical literacy. It enables learners to recognise the significance of historical events, understand the language used to describe them, and critically engage with the different interpretations that emerge from various contexts (Nippi, 2022). Conceptual understanding provides a lasting educational foundation that enables students to connect historical events with their own lives and contemporary issues. It positions historical knowledge and thinking as products of active dialogue between learners and past evidence, with language serving as the key medium. This process strengthens the ability to recall and evaluate historical events, enabling critical verification of perspectives.

The third dimension, source work (SW), shows a success rate of 65.41%, indicating that more than half of the respondents answered it correctly. Several factors may help explain this result. First, recent pedagogical approaches in history education in West Java have placed greater emphasis on inquiry-based learning and the use of primary sources, which provided students with more structured practice in evaluating documents, images, and other evidence. Some teachers in West Java also integrate local history into their classes by utilising local heritage. Second, teaching materials commonly used in schools increasingly integrate source excerpts and visual

representations (using images and videos), providing students with more frequent opportunities to practice source analysis. In addition, a teacher assigned students to interview historical figures and to search for primary sources. Unfortunately, not all history teachers practice a similar pedagogy. There are history teachers who have yet to optimise local cultural and historical heritage to stimulate students' Source Work skill because they are still fixated on textbooks.

Historical literacy is the ability to engage effectively with historical sources by understanding, interpreting, and managing them, which helps students navigate complex historical narratives and develop critical thinking skills (Maposa & Wassermann, 2009). The ability to evaluate the credibility of sources is indeed essential for achieving historical literacy. They need to investigate them by critically studying the historical sources and narratives from different perspectives, statements, and arguments. The inability to find and compare diverse historical narratives leads students to focus on the same accounts, making the teacher's role crucial in guiding them to access primary and secondary sources as well as varied perspectives.

Several factors underlie low historical literacy scores. The first deals with teachers who dominantly focus on memorising instead of improving students' critical thinking and analysis (Kumalasari et al., 2022; Purwanta, 2023). History teaching relies more on an expository approach, rather than discussions or debates. This results in a lack of motivation and historical narratives. To overcome, the implementation of information technology and interactive methods becomes the answer to improve students' involvement and imagination in learning history.

The second factor is curriculum design, emphasising basic historical facts without encouraging deeper analysis or understanding about the context and significance of the facts. Critics argue that this approach contributes to producing a generation of students who are "historically illiterate" (Maposa & Wassermann, 2009). The assessment that focuses on memorising also contributes to students' analysis skills. Therefore, teachers need to consider assessments, such as an assessment in the form of a project or essay writing, that enable students to elaborate their answer.

The third factor addresses the cultural context, showing that students study history that does not originate from their own region. In some cases, historical narratives taught may not resonate with students' cultural background, which increasingly isolates them from the subject matter. Furthermore, the development of digital technology and the prevalence of social media have both advantages and disadvantages for historical literacy. Digital tools and social media have benefits which allow audiences to connect with historians and make communities around the world, enrich history learning experiences by making them more interactive and appealing, and enhance engagement with historical events. Meanwhile, these two aspects also reduce students' engagement with historical content and their discernment in selecting information, leading to a decline in literacy skills. The speed and brevity of social media communication can reinforce superficial understandings of the past. At the same time, the prevalence of misinformation or biased narratives can undermine students' ability to evaluate historical accuracy. (Tikhonova & Artamonov, 2023)

Historical literacy shows no significant difference between genders. However, females have been reported to have a slightly higher level of historical literacy than males. This is in line with studies by Syamsuri & Bancong (2022) and Tiarina et al. (2022), which show that females have higher literacy than males. The intrinsic motivation to read significantly contributes to historical literacy, as learning history begins with enjoying reading history books Lee (2005) The first reason is that female students tend to have higher intrinsic motivation to read. Girls generally demonstrate more positive reading attitudes, stronger skills, and higher self-efficacy, which support their performance in historical literacy. The principal axes of historical literacy are understanding historical structure; knowing, understanding, and recognising the importance of historical facts; learning fact-finding methods and critical thinking; and linking the reading skills for historical texts with the ability to think (Nippi, 2022). Both family and peer influences shape reading habits. Girls benefit more from family interactions, which enhance their social skills, motivation, and reading achievement.

The second reason is that female students tend to show a greater inclination to focus on reading-related tasks (Syamsuri & Bancong, 2022). Female students tend to be meticulous in carrying out those activities and developing practical reading skills. From a cognitive theory perspective, women generally excel in verbal learning, memory, and language-related tasks, while men show strength in visuospatial working memory Halpern (2004) Since history instruction often relies heavily on text-based reading and memorisation, which align more closely with women's cognitive strengths, male students tend to score slightly lower in historical literacy.

The insignificant gender differences in low historical literacy scores highlight shared challenges that necessitate urgent improvements in history education through enhanced teaching strategies. Firstly, the integration of various historical research activities, from observation and source gathering to contextualization (De La Paz et al., 2014). It becomes possible by involving students in analysing historical events around them. Secondly, Reading Like a Historian (RLH), employing general procedures, may engage students in historical investigation activities (Collin & Reich, 2015). Thirdly, the use of film employing a model known as Facts, Form, and Reception (FFR). *Facts* are the preliminary stage of this approach; learners are acquainted with the historical context represented in the film, specifically the real events to which it refers. Upon completing the film viewing, students engage in a comprehensive analysis through a form that integrates both film and historical theory. The *reception* is the examination of the motivations behind the film's production during that specific period, the manner in which audiences perceived it, and the interpretations they ascribed to it through the utilization of primary sources (for instance, film critiques and public discourses regarding the film's significance) are articulated to address the matter of the film's second temporal context (Mavrommati & Repoussi, 2020). The fourth strategy is to assign a project to write a history essay and communicate it. In writing, students develop a basic understanding of the past and reconstruct significant events, requiring them to link their personal experiences to the past and the present, and are encouraged to express their thoughts through writing freely. To train writing skills, students must be able to develop their ideas in writing, with structure and language that conform to the rules. Teachers should give students opportunities to learn about life in that era using various sources, offer guiding questions, and model critical thinking to help them contextualise information. The fifth strategy, improving historical literacy

through RBL-STEM, enables students to recognise past events, understand narratives, demonstrate research skills, apply historical language, analyse concepts, and use ICT to explore historical documents (Collin & Reich, 2015).

Conclusion

The study confirms that historical literacy among students in West Java is generally low, with no significant difference between male and female learners, reflecting issues of rote memorisation, curriculum design, and social context. To address these issues, teachers should encourage students to investigate and explore various sources, and to engage in historical writing, utilising either print or digital media. Both genders struggle equally, which underscores the need for curriculum reform that prioritises the development of historical literacy. Strengthening teacher training, diversifying instructional resources, and integrating local as well as national historical contexts into the curriculum could provide pathways for improvement. Historical literacy will shape a younger generation that is historically aware, critical, and concerned about their nation. While this study provides important insights into students' historical literacy in West Java, Indonesia, its geographic scope is limited. Future research across other regions and countries is needed to test the broader applicability of these findings.

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